

Exploration of rural revitalization in areas rich in historical and cultural resources

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Abstract: Many of China's villages are found in regions with a wealth of cultural assets but a weak economy. In Chinese social theory and practice, the vitality and revitalization of these villages is a contentious and contentious issue. This essay uses the West Shanxi traditional area as its research subject, summarizing the opportunities and difficulties of rural development while also examining the inner force behind it. These villages, in our opinion, must find solutions to the major issues of industry, population, and style. These villages can only regain their vitality and follow the development path of a virtuous cycle by developing strategies from a development perspective.

Keywords: Cultural Resources; Rural Revitalization; Industry; Population; Style

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Preface

China is home to numerous villages in regions with a wealth of historical and cultural treasures. The production, existence, and communication of the residents are carried by these villages. Some of them, owing to the difficult living conditions, isolation, and other factors, have turned into economically depressed villages [1]. The authenticity of culture and life forms can be preserved because rural development is slow and closed. However, how to balance the relationship between authenticity and rural revitalization in the context of rapid economic development and rural resurgence is a topic we need to research.

1. The Current Situation of Rural Resources Development in The Cultural Resources' Rich Areas in Western Shanxi

1.1 Distribution of Rural Cultural Resources in Western Shanxi

The Western region of Shanxi Province has complex and diverse landforms as well as a lengthy history, which have shaped the fundamental elements of this region's thick and rich rural history and culture. West Shanxi is situated on the Yellow River's bank and serves as an important economic corridor connecting Shanxi to northwest Gansu and Ningxia. On the one hand, the historical culture there was passed down from the old villages has authenticity and

diversity. During the Ming and Qing Dynasties, some villages along the Yellow River and Qiushui River in the mountain area of Western Shanxi relied on geographical advantages to carry out business transfer activities, becoming prosperous commercial post stations, and making the area rich in Shanxi Merchants' history and culture; Moreover, this area is the old revolutionary base where stories such as the biography of heroes of Luliang and Liang dynasties took place. It is the base of the Eighth Route Army in the Anti-Japanese war. He Long, Xi Zhongxun and other revolutionaries of the older generation fought and lived here, and there are many revolutionary historical sites and stories of heroic battles. Therefore, the unique farming culture, folk culture and revolutionary culture are preserved in Western Shanxi, which reflect a variety of historical and cultural customs, all of which are worth cherishing and using.

1.2 Rural Economic Resources in Western Shanxi

Coal mines and other mineral resources make up Western Shanxi's industrial resources. This region has abundant, widely dispersed, and favorable mining conditions. In Shanxi Province, it is a significant source of energy resources. These resources haven't, however, given the neighboring villages' economies much of a boost. The majority of the villages in Western Shanxi do not currently have the authority to own or manage coal mines. Therefore, the revenue from state-owned coal mines has no bearing on the overall economy of villages. On the other hand, village landscapes have been harmed by environmental pollution. The agricultural production of traditional villages in Western Shanxi has been extensive farming for a long time, with a primitive production mode, a single product, and low output because the cultivated land resources are very scarce, the per capita cultivated land area is lower than the national average level, and is affected by the natural climate and landform. Agriculture has developed into a situation where it is dependent on the weather, which has led to the unfavorable development of animal husbandry and no economic scale benefit. The benefits of port city also vanished as a result of the ongoing wars in Western Shanxi in modern times and the deterioration of Yellow River waterway transportation. Western Shanxi's business climate was destroyed, making Shanxi merchants here history.

1.3 Rural Population Resources in Western Shanxi

At present, many ancient villages and traditional villages in China have the phenomenon of hollow villages and aging population, and the ancient villages in the mountainous area of Western Shanxi are no exception. With the development of society, young people are affected by the modern lifestyle and are eager to pursue a better quality of life. Therefore, increasingly young, and middle-aged workers on the ancient village in Western Shanxi go out of their homes to work in economically developed areas, resulting in the rising proportion of registered residence population. At the same time, due to the pursuit of convenience stores or the influence of children's education, a considerable number of residents have moved to workplaces, and most of the remaining residents in the village are the elderly. At present, the proportion of the actual resident population in some villages in Western Shanxi in the registered residence population has decreased year by year, and some villages have formed what people call "hollow villages" [2]. Among the permanent population, the proportion of women is greater than that of men, and the left behind children lack parental education, thus forming a series of social problems.

2. Opportunities and Challenges for The Development of Villages Rich in History and Culture in Western Shanxi

2.1 Opportunities

1. Rural revitalization strategy

The 19th CPC National Congress proposed the implementation of the Rural Revitalization Strategy [3]. Urban and rural areas coexist and depend on each other to form the main space of human life. Rural areas are the embryonic urban complex with natural, social, and economic functions. Cities are born because of villages, and villages are born because of cities. The implementation of the Rural Revitalization Strategy is the main means to solve the imbalance between urban and rural development. The rural economic and cultural revitalization in the vast areas rich in historical and cultural resources is facing major opportunities.

2. Advantages of old revolutionary base areas

The old revolutionary base areas are the foundation of Chinese country and the historical testimony of the Chinese people's revolution. It is of special political significance to let the people in the old revolutionary base areas gradually live a rich and happy life. The opinions on supporting the revitalization and development of old revolutionary base areas in the new era points out that it is necessary to accelerate the improvement of the infrastructure of old revolutionary base areas, develop characteristic industrial system, improve innovation ability, cultivate new kinetic energy for the revitalization and development of old revolutionary base areas, and improve economic quality, efficiency and core competitiveness, which is an important guide for the development of old revolutionary base areas in Western Shanxi [4].

3. Traditional architectural features

The most remarkable architectural feature in Western Shanxi is the mountain architectural settlement, whose architectural form is the combination of kiln and house. The layout of local kilns is adapted to local conditions, and they are exceptionally good at using the terrain height difference to organize the spatial sense of the building group; At the same time, this construction method of making full use of mountains to build residential buildings also won a lot of arable land for plain area. At present, some of the houses newly built by villagers also have traditional layout and decoration characteristics, reflecting the inheritance of regional culture.

2.2 Challenges

1. Education lags behind

The lag of education is caused by the uneven distribution of educational resources, the imperfect supporting resources of local education, which affects the local education level, and some villagers migrate to cities and towns due to the education problems of their children. Because the actual resident population in rural areas is gradually decreasing, some rural primary schools have been gradually removed and merged. Only large-scale and economically developed villages have primary schools, and secondary schools are only distributed in towns or counties, which has a direct impact on the lives of villagers. Moreover, rural teachers have no staffing guarantee, and their income level is low, so they cannot feel at ease to provide good educational services in the countryside. The population emigration caused by this situation makes the brain drain form a vicious circle, which cannot provide talent and intellectual security for the revitalization of such rural areas.

2. Backward industry

Although the rise of traditional villages in the Western Shanxi Mountain area is based on agricultural culture, due to the lack of flatland, many cultivated lands has been developed on the hillside, and soil erosion is profoundly serious

after many trees have been cut down. The fertility of the land decreased after over cultivation. After the reform and opening, the proportion of agriculture in village industry gradually decreased. However, the small scale of local industries, scattered industries and no own brand restrict the development of rural secondary and tertiary industries in Western Shanxi, resulting in the gradual migration of surplus rural labor in Western Shanxi to foreign cities.

3. Development damage

In recent years, under the multiple challenges and impacts of agricultural modernization, rural urbanization, new rural construction and so on, the remote villages in Western Shanxi continue to suffer constructive damage. Following the example of the city, the overall rural planning did not adapt to local conditions. Due to the village regulations, coupled with the lack of management and other reasons, some modern buildings with modern features or lofty standards were built. These heterogeneous elements have damaged the spatial pattern of the village. Moreover, most of the new buildings were built in plain area, lacking respect for cultivated land. It is urgent to plan, protect and guide the development of ancient villages.

2.3 Internal Driving Force of Development Needs

Finally, the development of traditional villages is economic development, which is a crucial link for the protection of traditional villages. From the perspective of sustainable development of resources, the traditional villages in Western Shanxi can consider to vigorously develop ecological tourism based on modern ecological planting industry. We should make full use of the advantages of convenient transportation, integrate the local economic development circle, make use of existing resources, actively participate in regional joint development, and form the scale benefits of cluster development.

3. Three Key Issues to Be Solved in The Revitalization of similar Villages

3.1 Industrial Problems

Western Shanxi is a mountainous area located on the Loess Plateau. Soil erosion and barren mountain resources are a problem that cannot be ignored. At the same time, many ancient villages in Western Shanxi have developed based on the traditional farming culture. However, due to the influence of terrain and climate, the water resources in mountainous areas are scarce, which has led to the fact that the local agricultural planting has been an extensive agriculture relying on the weather for a long time. The production technology is backward, which not only has low output, but also has no characteristics, and cannot form a brand.

Since the founding of People's republic of China, the pace of social development has accelerated. Relying on the waterway transportation of the Yellow River can no longer meet the needs of social development, and the transportation industry and Commerce will inevitably decline. Before modern times, the Western Shanxi Mountain area lived on animal husbandry. After the reform and opening, affected by national policies and modern science and technology, the agriculture in the Western Shanxi Mountain area has developed partially. However, due to the limitations of terrain and water resources, agricultural production has not improved. In addition, the mountain area in Western Shanxi is affected by land transportation restrictions, and the cultivated land resources are insufficient. Therefore, agricultural production cannot meet the population growth and people's demand for a better life. In general, the rural poverty

caused by the lack of obvious pillar industries has become the core problem of traditional villages in Western Shanxi mountainous areas.

3.2 Ecological and Human Settlements

West Shanxi is in the hinterland of the Loess Plateau, and the situation of soil erosion is serious. On the one hand, the local terrain has become crisscrossed with gullies and no large area of flat land. On the other hand, the erosion of rainwater has taken away the nutrients in the soil, making the land barren, and a large amount of soil has been washed into the Yellow River, causing serious flooding in the downstream areas. At the same time, the forest vegetation coverage in Western Shanxi is low, the groundwater level is reduced due to the massive exploitation of coal resources, and there is no primary River in the region. Therefore, most mountain villages lack water for production and living, and only the villages passing by the Yellow River and its tributaries have their water resources problems alleviated to a certain extent. The soil in Western Shanxi is very suitable for excavating caves. Many people's houses are cliff kilns dug out of cliffs. Its low cost, adapt to the local climate, has a strong feasibility. However, it is undeniable that many cases have been weathered for a long time, and due to the substantial number of deforestations of mountain vegetation, this has an enormous potential safety hazard to the buildings and roads of ancient villages. Due to the influence of natural geographical environment and economic foundation, the infrastructure of ancient villages is not perfect, among which the most serious is the water supply and drainage problem. It is difficult for some villages to obtain drinking water, which brings great inconvenience to the lives of residents. In addition, the drainage facilities are not perfect, and there are certain potential safety hazards for the mountainous areas of the Loess Plateau.

3.3 Inheritance of Historical Features

Throughout Shanxi, the buildings in the mountainous areas of Western Shanxi have incredibly significant characteristics of the Loess Plateau in Western Shanxi. The value of local traditional villages is reflected in the spatial pattern of settlements, the spatial pattern of streets and alleys, as well as the architectural style and folk culture. However, with the continuous acceleration of urbanization in recent years, especially in the past two years, the national poverty alleviation work has further expanded and finally entered the final stage. Many villages are actively promoting the reconstruction of dilapidated houses and the renovation and construction of related dwellings, which has led to the demolition of many ancient dwellings, and the villagers' awareness of protection is extremely weak. They believe that old houses and ancient heritage are the embodiment of poverty and backwardness, Therefore, many architectural relics have been destructively destroyed, which has affected the traditional pattern and architectural style of ancient villages. In addition, today's school-age children go out to school, and the middle-aged and young generation go out to work. The folk culture and artisanship of the older generation face the dilemma of no successor and no inheritance.

4. Development Path and Strategy of Virtuous Circle

4.1 Rural Governance Innovation

In the context of implementing the Rural Revitalization Strategy, we must first adhere to the leadership of the Communist Party of China, promote the advantages of institutionalization, consolidate, and improve the basic rural management system, and innovate the rural governance system. The leaders of the rural Party committee should, according to the actual situation of the countryside and the rural revitalization Road proposed by General Secretary Xi, walk out of the revitalization road suitable for the development of the village, actively explore innovative governance

strategies on the premise of protecting traditional characteristics, and inject internal development power into the countryside.

1. Institutional advantages

The national system of our country is progressing with the development of society and has vitality. The coordination of productive forces and production relations is the concentrated embodiment of China's institutional advantages. Therefore, to make the governance efficiency benign, we must conform to and promote the advantages of the system.

The leadership of the party is the greatest advantage of our national system. Only by adhering to and improving the leadership of the party can we keep pace with the times, give full play to the advantages of the system, and maximize the efficiency of governance. The leaders of rural Party committees need to continue to practice, following the leadership of the party, promote governance modernization and institutional innovation, absorb the governance experience of cities or villages, and liberate and develop local productivity, to better promote the revitalization of villages and lead people out of poverty and get rich.

2. Technology introduction

Internet is an indispensable technology today. With the vigorous development of the Internet and the growing needs of the people, remote villages are also connected to cables and wireless networks. In order to give full play to the efficient and convenient advantages of Internet technology, accelerate the development of various emerging services based on the Internet, and innovate the government service mode, China has successively issued a series of policy documents on "Internet + government service", aiming to use Internet technology to promote political services and meet public needs. Rural political commissar leaders need to follow the situation, introduce new technologies and apply them to rural governance, introduce talents, strengthen the exploration of the "blockchain +" [5] proposed by General Secretary Xi in people's livelihood areas, and promote the safe, orderly and standardized development of government services, so as to make rural governance develop well.

3. Digital intelligence innovation

The key to rural governance decision-making lies in "data". The collection of data makes the number and scope of governance more in-depth control, makes the combination of individuals and the whole run through, and improves the rural governance ability and level. "Digital intelligence" enables rural governance to collect rural development trends and residents' population opinions in a diversified manner, and understand residents' demands in a timelier manner, to provide services and governance directions more accurately.

4. Industrial prosperity

i. Characteristic industry

From the perspective of sustainable development of resources, traditional villages in Western Shanxi can consider taking modern ecological planting industry as the basis to further improve the commodity rate of agricultural products, develop deep processing of agricultural products, extend the agricultural industrial chain, and develop ecological

sightseeing tourism. Expand sales channels, promote the circulation of agricultural products, improve farmers' income, and achieve profitable development.

With the continuous development of social economy, the revitalization of rural areas in Western Shanxi needs to do large-scale industries. Contiguous industrial parks are the direction of current and future industrial development. To revitalize rural industries, we must take the road of large-scale, scientific, and branded contiguous development. We must give full play to the role of cooperatives, make effective use of collective land and idle land, connect industries into pieces, improve the advantages of industrial scale, and enable rural industries to do well, go out and form your own characteristic brand.

ii. Tourism driven

Make full use of local characteristic planting and breeding to promote the development of tertiary industries such as tourism. Create a tourism industry suitable for the characteristics of rural environment. Using modern agriculture to develop farmhouse entertainment and picking entertainment, it will be built into an eco-village for tourism and vacation in surrounding towns. Ancient villages in Western Shanxi have high cultural, and ecological values. Therefore, the ancient village can carry out relevant cooperation with many colleges and universities and take the village as a student sketch practice base. Villages can learn from this model or carry out corporate operation and carry out relevant cooperation as an extension of the ancient village industry. At the same time, we can cooperate with relevant universities and scientific research and design institutes to carry out in-depth protection research on traditional dwellings, to realize scientific protection and utilization.

iii. Cultural sustainability

At the same time of development, choose projects with local resources as raw materials and traditional skills as characteristics, carry forward traditional processes, and develop the commercial value of local products, to achieve the purpose of carrying forward traditional processes and traditional culture. We should not only inherit traditional culture, but also use its economic value to realize the combination of sustainable development and cultural protection. Build cultural relics and historic sites in historical villages with complete historical resources; In villages with distinctive ecological resources, landscape tourism routes can be organized on a larger scale; Develop revolutionary cultural tourism projects in villages with revolutionary sites to achieve a win-win situation of historical inheritance and economic development. Only from the perspective of resources and combined with the local cultural characteristics, can we inherit and carry forward the history, culture of ancient villages, and realize the revitalization and sustainable development of ancient villages.

5. Population regression

To make hollow villages popular, we must solve the problem of labor returning home first. Only by solving the problems of education retention and industry attraction, can we achieve the three considerations of hometown employment, children going to school and taking care of the elderly.

i. Industry attraction

Any development needs to rely on labor, and Rural Revitalization needs to introduce talents. We should make heroic efforts to attract talents, cultivate industry leaders, formulate detailed talent recruitment, and return plans, and

provide good services and help for young entrepreneurs in the township. Focusing on the development of agricultural production and the goal of increasing farmers' income, we will actively carry out activities to revitalize agriculture through science and technology. Vigorously support the "one village, one product" or "multiple villages, one product" industries. Only by continuing to encourage the development of modern agriculture that benefits farmers, while adhering to the road of agricultural industrialization, can returnees succeed in starting businesses at home, can they gather talent for Rural Revitalization and consolidate the foundation for Rural Revitalization.

ii. Education retention

We should continue to increase investment, attract more outstanding talents to devote themselves to rural education, and promote the balanced development of urban and rural education. This requires improving the school running conditions of rural primary and secondary schools and implementing the establishment of rural teachers' identity and living subsidies. Poor students who file and file their cards enjoy full coverage of the subsidy policy, the construction of schools and kindergartens in poor villages, and the technical training of poor families.

iii. Return of family affection

The main owners of ancient villages are local villagers. To promote the revitalization of rural culture and better protect and develop ancient villages, ideological and moral construction and family culture construction are extremely important. Nowadays, with the improvement of material life, the cultural quality of villagers should also be improved. We should deeply excavate the local clan culture, enhance the villagers' awareness of their hometown, recognize the beauty of their hometown, strengthen the villagers' sense of belonging and identity, and carry forward their development. Cultivate a good rural style and family style. Only by strengthening the awareness of family ties in their hometown can we provide the necessary premise for the protection and development of ancient villages.

6. Style protection

The natural resources, landscape pattern and the spatial form of the main part of the ancient villages in the mountainous area of Western Shanxi have their own regional characteristics. Most of the ancient villages in Western Shanxi are formed according to the mountain. Therefore, it is necessary to do an excellent job in returning the construction to farming or returning the construction to forestry, to lay a good foundation for the development of agriculture, tourism, forestry, and other industries with ancient village characteristics. Based on paying attention to the overall pattern, we should deal with the traditional residential buildings inside the ancient village, formulate classification and regulation guidelines according to the characteristics of its style, and guide the harmony and unity of the overall architectural style of the ancient village. For buildings that are inconsistent with the style of traditional villages or buildings with poor construction quality, we should extract the elements of traditional buildings in villages and apply these elements to the renovation and improvement of the facade of buildings, to achieve the purpose of coordination and unity with the style of traditional villages. The internal environment of the courtyard and the interior of the building should be renewed, and improved, and modern living facilities should be provided to improve the living conditions, to meet the modern living needs and lifestyle of residents and improve the quality of life.

5. Conclusion

Under the policy background of vigorously promoting the development of Rural Revitalization in China, this paper analyzes the obstacles faced by the historical and cultural rich villages in Western Shanxi in the new development period from the aspects of population, industrial resources, value inheritance of human settlements and so on; And from the aspects of rural governance innovation, industry, population and style, it provides optional innovative strategies for the township party and government to comply with national policies in rural governance, and puts forward practical measures for the protection and development of such villages. It aims to carry forward the characteristic traditional culture of Western Shanxi, realize the combination of the protection and sustainable development of ancient villages, and hope to provide some reference for the development of historical and culturally rich villages in Western Shanxi.

Notes:

1. Depression refers to the terrain with high surrounding and low middle; Economic depression refers to the economic indicators lower than the level of surrounding cities.
2. Economically, hollow village means that with the process of urbanization and industrialization in China, many rural young and middle-aged people are pouring into cities to work and live in cities. Therefore, the population left in rural areas is a phenomenon of old, weak, sick, and disabled. Because its rural resident population is like the hollow of a big tree, it is named hollow village.
3. The report of the 19th National Congress of the Communist Party of China proposed "implementing the Rural Revitalization Strategy". In December 2017, the central rural work conference further pointed out "taking the road of Socialist Rural Revitalization with Chinese characteristics". Then, on February 4, 2018, the No. 1 central document "the opinions of the State Council of the Communist Party of China on implementing the Rural Revitalization Strategy" was issued, which put forward the overall deployment for the current plan of formulating and implementing the Rural Revitalization Strategy in all parts of China.
4. On February 20, 2021, the State Council issued the "opinions on supporting the revitalization and development of the old revolutionary base areas in the new era", which fully reflects the deep concern of the Party Central Committee and the State Council for the people of the old revolutionary base areas. It is a programmatic document to support the revitalization and development of the old revolutionary base areas during the 14th five year plan and even longer.
5. Blockchain is a new application mode of computer technology, such as distributed data storage, point-to-point transmission, consensus mechanism, encryption algorithm, etc. It is a decentralized database. The national Internet Information Office issued the regulations on the management of blockchain information services on January 10, 2019, which will be implemented from February 15, 2019.

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